

Minimizing of Forecasting Error in Fuzzy Time Series Model Using Graph-Based Clustering Method

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ABSTRACT: In recent years, numerous fuzzy time series (FTS) forecasting models have been developed to address complex and incomplete problems. However, the accuracy of these models is specific to the problem at hand and varies across datasets. Despite claims of superiority over traditional statistical and single machine learning-based models, achieving improved forecasting accuracy remains a formidable challenge. In FTS models, the lengths of intervals and fuzzy relationship groups are considered crucial factors influencing forecasting accuracy. Hence, this study introduces an FTS forecasting model based on the graph-based clustering technique. The clustering algorithm, utilized during the fuzzification stage, enables the derivation of unequal interval lengths. The proposed model is applied to forecast two numerical datasets: enrollment data from the University of Alabama and the datasets of Gas prices RON95 in Vietnam. Comparisons of forecasting results between the proposed model and others are conducted for enrollment forecasts at the University of Alabama. The findings reveal that the proposed model achieves higher forecasting accuracy across all orders of fuzzy relationships when compared to its counterparts.

KEYWORDS: Enrolments, RON95, forecasting, FTS, fuzzy logical relationships, graph - based clustering

I. INTRODUCTION

Forecasting daily events like temperature, stock market trends, population growth, and crop production poses a significant challenge in forecasting. While achieving perfect accuracy may be unattainable, minimizing errors is crucial. Traditional models like Autoregressive (AR), Moving Average (MA), and Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) rely on linear assumptions and extensive historical data. In contrast, Fuzzy Time Series (FTS) models, pioneered by Song and Chissom [1, 2], offer flexibility with fuzzy relational matrices but struggle with interval determination and computational complexity. To address these issues, Chen's first-order FTS model [3] employs simpler arithmetic operations instead of complex max-min operators, leading to improved prediction accuracy. Subsequent research has explored various enhancements, including equal and different interval lengths [4-8], refined fuzzy relationship groups [9-16], and defuzzification processes [17-19]. Additionally, high-order FTS models [20-23] have emerged to overcome the limitations of first-order models, with efforts to reduce computational complexity and improve accuracy in predicting university enrollments and crop production. Recently, numerous researchers have integrated intelligent computational techniques with various FTS models to tackle intricate forecasting challenges. For instance, Lee et al. [20] explored a two – factor high-order FTS model for temperature prediction and TAIFEX. They also employed an annealing technique [21] to optimize division lengths for enhanced forecasting accuracy. Additionally, Chen and Chung [22] utilized a genetic algorithm (GA) to optimize intervals

within the universal of discourse, introducing both first-order and high-order forecasting models to predict Alabama university enrollments. Another approach, Chen and Wang [23] employs involves using automatic clustering techniques to build fuzzy time series forecasting models for temperature and TAIFEX (Taiwan Futures Exchange) problems. Presently, the utilization of particle swarm optimization (PSO) to select optimal intervals in fuzzy time series forecasting models has garnered considerable attention. Research demonstrates that PSO-based interval selection significantly enhances forecasting model performance [24, 25]. For instance, Kuo et al. [13] proposed a novel forecasting model by integrating PSO with FTS to enhance prediction accuracy and devised a new defuzzification rule for TAIFEX prediction. Similarly, studies [23, 26] introduced two-factor high-order FTS models for forecasting the Taiwan stock market and TAIFEX, utilizing PSO for interval optimization. Furthermore, Park et al. [27] proposed a PSO-enhanced two-factor high-order FTS model for more accurate forecasting results. Huarng et al. [19] introduced a hybrid predictive model incorporating PSO to rectify output prediction rules for university admissions. Research work [16] proposes a novel probabilistic intuitionistic FTS forecasting model using support vector machine to address both uncertainty and non-determinism associated with real world time series data. Cheng et al. [28] proposed an FTS model for TAIFEX prediction, employing PSO for interval length determination and the K-means algorithm for fuzzy set indexing. Various techniques such as raw clustering [9], automatic clustering [10],

and fuzzy C-Mean clustering [25] have been introduced to determine interval length in recent studies.

Analyzing the aforementioned works reveals that determining appropriate interval length, establishing fuzzy relationships, and formulating output prediction rules pose significant challenges and substantially impact predictive accuracy. Additionally, incorporating observed factors beyond the main forecasted factor is crucial for enhancing predictive efficiency. Despite notable progress in interval length determination and output prediction rule exploitation, these challenges continue to captivate researchers' attention. In an effort to enhance the predictive efficiency of FTS forecasting models, this study proposes a novel forecasting model utilizing a graph-based clustering technique to determine interval lengths using dataset of Gas prices RON95 in Vietnam. Initially, we propose a new algorithm for optimal interval length determination using a graph-based clustering approach. Subsequently, we define fuzzy sets based on these intervals and fuzzify historical data. Based on these fuzzified values, fuzzy relationships are derived, followed by the formation of fuzzy relationship groups (FRGs) according to chronological order. Finally, these FRGs are utilized to derive forecasting results employing a weighted defuzzification method.

The remaining sections of this paper are structured as follows: Section 2 provides fundamental definitions of fuzzy time series and algorithms. In Section 3, a forecasting model that integrates FTS with a Graph-based clustering algorithm is presented. Section 4 assesses the performance of the models and compares the results with those obtained from other models. Finally, Section 5 offers concluding remarks.

II. THE FUNDAMENTAL THEORIES

In this section, we briefly introduce general knowledge related to FTS which is proposed in [1-3] and improved by research work in [4].

2.1. Fuzzy time series

The concepts of FTS were defined by Song and Chissom [2, 3], in which the historical data are given in the form of fuzzy sets [1]. Assume that $Y(t)$ ($t = \dots, 0, 1, 2 \dots$) a real subset R ($Y(t) \subseteq R$), regarded as the UoD on which the fuzzy sets $f_i(t)$ ($i = 1, 2 \dots$) are defined. If $F(t)$ including the collection of $f_1(t), f_2(t), \dots$, then $F(t)$ is namely an FTS which is defined on $Y(t)$.

If there exists fuzzy relationship (FR) between $F(t - 1)$ and $F(t)$, namely $R(t - 1, t)$, such that they can be expressed as $F(t) = F(t - 1) * R(t - 1, t)$ or $F(t - 1) \rightarrow F(t)$; Where $R(t - 1, t)$ is the first-order fuzzy relationship between $F(t)$ and $F(t - 1)$ and "*" represents the max-min composition operator. Here $F(t)$ and $F(t - 1)$ are fuzzy sets. If, let $A_i = F(t)$ and $A_j = F(t-1)$, the relationship between $F(t)$ and $F(t - 1)$ is replaced by $A_i \rightarrow A_j$, where A_i and A_j are called the current state and the next state of fuzzy relationship, respectively.

Let $F(t)$ be a fuzzy time series. If $F(t)$ is derived by more fuzzy sets $F(t - 1), F(t - 2), \dots, F(t - m + 1), F(t - m)$, then fuzzy relationship between them can be represented as $F(t - m), \dots, F(t - 2), F(t - 1) \rightarrow F(t)$. This relationship is called the m - order FTS model [3]

The fuzzy logical relationships having the same left-hand side can be further grouped into a Fuzzy relationship group [4]. Assume there are exists FLRs as follows: $A_i \rightarrow A_{k1}, A_i \rightarrow A_{k2}, \dots, A_i \rightarrow A_{km}$; these FLRs can be put into the same FRG as: $A_i \rightarrow A_{k1}, A_{k2}, \dots, A_{km}$.

In order to generate the forecasting rules, the approach involves building fuzzy relationships through time-variant grouping, also known as censusing [25]. This entails computing the fuzzy relationships established from the training dataset based on identical left-hand sides and right-hand sides at the time of forecasting relative to previous instances.

2.2. Graph based clustering algorithm (GBC)

Graph-based clustering algorithms have demonstrated a remarkable ability to produce results that align closely with human intuition [29]. A defining feature shared in graph-based clustering methods is the utilization of a graph constructed from the dataset during the clustering process [30]. In these methods, data entities are represented as nodes within a graph, with connections established between related entities. Clusters are formed when a group of entities is interconnected but lacks connectivity to entities outside the group. Building upon these principles, our research introduces a novel data clustering approach [31], wherein the dataset is represented as a tree structure, and clusters are automatically generated without requiring the user to pre-specify the number of clusters. Specifically, the graph-based clustering method can be outlined in four distinct procedures as follows:

- (1) Root node location procedure (RNLP). This technique identifies the root node based on the provided data.
- (2) Node insertion procedure (NIP). This technique inserts one element of the dataset and root node and places the elements in the proper position.
- (3) Tree making procedure (TMP). This procedure displays the tree from the provided data set and the root node.
- (4) Clustering procedure (CP) based on nodes in the tree. This process makes logical node clustering using the tree that the TMP generated as input.

III. A PROPOSED FORECASTING MODEL COMBINING FTS AND GBC

The objective of this Section is to propose a hybrid FTS forecasting model which is incorporated between the Graph-based clustering and FTS. The framework of forecasting proposed model includes six steps which is presented in Fig. 1. To handle these steps, all The datasets of Gas prices RON95 in Vietnam from 02/10/2023 to 28/03/2024 are depicted in Fig.2, which are utilized for illustrating forecasted process. The details of steps of the proposed model are explained as following:

Fig. 1: The flowchart illustrating the proposed forecasting model employing Graph-based clustering.

Fig. 2: The datasets of Gas prices RON95 in Vietnam which was collected from <https://vnexpress.net/kinhdoanh/hang-hoa>

Step 1: Partitioning dataset into intervals using graph-based clustering

This step applies graph-based clustering algorithm in Section 2.2 to partition historical dataset into clusters, and then, adjust them into intervals with unequal-size. The calculation is described according to sub-steps as follows:

Step 1.1: Apply the graph-based clustering algorithm to partition data into C clusters.

To partition time series $X(t)$ into C clusters, four procedures of the graph-based clustering algorithm in Section 2.2 are used in this step. The brief results of these four procedures are explained as below:

1) Root node location procedure.

Input the dataset of of Gas prices RON95 as: $X(t) = (24840, 23040, \dots, 24280, 24810)$ with $(02/10/2023 \leq t \leq 28/03/2024)$

$$\text{Calculate range } Rg = \text{MAX}_{value} - \text{MIN}_{value} = 3440$$

Calculate standard deviation of the time series as $SD = 925.07$

$$w = \frac{Rg}{SD * N} = 0.15$$

Define universe of discourse (U) of the S:

$$U = [\text{Min}_{value} - w, \text{Max}_{value} + w] = [21399.85, 24840.15];$$

Calculate midpoint of U: $\text{Mid}_u = (\text{Min}_{value} + \text{Max}_{value}) / 2$

= 23120

Assign the Mid_u as root node: $\text{Root} = \text{Mid}_u = 23120$

2) Node insertion procedure and Tree making procedure.

For making the tree, from the input dataset S and Root. We utilize two procedures TMP and NIP to make tree and insert nodes into the tree. The results of these two procedures are shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3: The tree represents the input data of Gas prices RON95 time series

3) Make the clusters based on Procedure 4 (CP)

After creating the data tree as shown in Fig.3, the procedure of making clusters is brief explained according to conditions as follows.

1. Initially, check that Root exists or not and check that Root has left (Root. LEFT) and right (Root. RIGHT)
2. If both children exist for each Root, then compute the difference between values of the Root and Root. RIGHT, and Root and Root. LEFT. Then make a cluster with corresponding child (either Root. LEFT or Root. RIGHT) and Root, which have the minimum difference.
3. If only one child existing for each Root, then make the cluster with either Root and Root. LEFT or Root and Root. RIGHT.
4. Repeat conditions 2-3, until all the value of the nodes in the tree are added to the clusters.

From Procedures above, we achieve 7 clusters and their corresponding cluster centers. Then, these clusters are sorted according to an ascending sequence of clustering centers, the final results are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: The Completed Clusters From The Ron95 Dataset

Number of clusters	Clusters C_i
1	(21400, 22140, 21910)
2	(22140)
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6	(23400, 23260, 23920)
7	(24840, 23510)

Step 1.2: Adjust the clusters into intervals.

Based on the obtained clusters, we adjust them into contiguous intervals according to the principles [25]

This step, the clusters in Table 1 are altered into intervals in accordance with cluster centres. Assume that V_{i+1} is the adjacent clustering centre next to V_i and each cluster C_i is assigned as an interval u_i , then the upper bound value of interval u_i ($Interval_UB_i$) and the lower bound value of interval u_{i+1} ($Interval_LB_{i+1}$) can be computed as follows:

$$Interval_UB_i = \frac{V_i + V_{i+1}}{2} \quad (1)$$

$$Interval_LB_{i+1} = Interval_UB_i \quad (2)$$

Because of lacking of the lower bound value for the first interval and lacking of the upper bound value for the last interval, the lower and upper bounds of these intervals are formed from the minimum element of the first cluster and the maximum element of the last cluster, respectively.

Compute midpoint value of the interval u_i as follows:

$$Mid_point_i = \frac{Interval_LB_i + Interval_UB_i}{2} \quad (3)$$

After applying the conditions above, we obtain 7 intervals corresponding to the clusters in Table 1, called u_i ($1 \leq i \leq 7$) and the midpoint values of these intervals are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: The Result Of Intervals And It's Midpoints

No	Intervals (u_i)	Midpoint
1	[21400 - 21978.35)	21689.2
2	[21978.35, 22270)	22124.2
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6	[23303.35, 23850.85)	23577.1
7	[23850.85, 24840]	24345.4

Step 2: Determine linguistic terms for each of interval obtained in Step 1

Each linguistic term can be defined by intervals that the historical time series data is distributed among these intervals. For ten intervals in step 1, we obtain 7 linguistic values of linguistic variables “RON95” which can be represented by fuzzy sets A_i , eg, $\{A_1, A_2, A_3, \dots, A_9, A_{15}\}$, respectively and calculated as follows:

$$A_i = a_{i1}/u_1 + a_{i2}/u_2 + \dots + a_{ij}/u_j + \dots + a_{i7}/u_7 \quad (4)$$

Where, the values $a_{ij} \in [0,1]$ indicates the grade of membership of u_j in fuzzy set A_i . The degree of each data is determined according to their membership grade to the fuzzy sets and which is defined in (5). Here, the symbol ‘+’ denotes the set union operator and the symbol ‘/’ denotes the membership of u_j which belongs to A_i . The value of a_{ij} is defined as follows:

$$a_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & j = i \\ 0.5 & j = i - 1 \text{ or } j = i + 1 \\ 0 & \text{others} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Step 3: Fuzzy all historical time series data

Each interval obtained in Step 1 can cover one or more

historical data value of time series. In order to all historical time series, the common way is to convert historical data which belongs to the interval U into fuzzy sets. If the maximum membership value of fuzzy set A_i occurs at u_i , then the fuzzified historical value is considered as A_i . For example, the RON95 data on day 02/10/2023 equal to 24840 belongs to the interval $u_7 = [23850.85, 24840]$ and the highest membership value of fuzzy set A_7 occurs at u_7 . So, it is fuzzified into A_7 . The similar way for next years, we complete the results of fuzzification of enrolments data for all years, as listed in Table 3.

Table 3: The Complete Fuzzified Results

Day	Actual data	Fuzzy sets
02/10/2023	24840	A_7
11/10/2023	23040	A_4
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21/03/2024	24280	A_7
28/03/2024	24810	A_7

Step 4: Create all m^{th} - order FRs between the fuzzified data values. ($m \geq 1$).

After converting data values of time series into fuzzy sets, the m^{th} -order FRs is created between two or many consecutive fuzzified values in time series. For establishing of these relationships, we need to find any relationship which has the type $F(t - m), F(t - m + 1), \dots, F(t - 1) \rightarrow F(t)$, where, the left - hand side of FR is called the current state and the right - hand side of FR is called next state, respectively. Then, the m^{th} - order FR is replaced by relation in accordance with the corresponding fuzzy sets as: $A_{im}, A_{i(m-1)}, \dots, A_{i2}, A_{i1} \rightarrow A_k$.

For example, with $m = 1$. From Table 4, it can be seen that the fuzzified historical data of time series on the day $t - 1$ of 02/10/2023 and t of 11/10/2023 are fuzzy sets A_7 and A_4 , respectively. The structure of the first - order FRs is created by two consecutive fuzzy sets as $A_7 \rightarrow A_4$, we have achieved the 1st-order FRs for the all fuzzified data values, which are presented in column 4 of Table 4.

Where, the linguistic value of $F(28/03/2024)$ on the right - hand side of the last relationship is denoted by symbol ‘#’ which is used to represent the unknown linguistic value.

Table 4. The Complete The 1st-Order Fuzzy Relationships

Day	No	Fuzzy set	1st- order FRs
02/10/2023		A_7	
11/10/2023	1	A_4	$A_7 \rightarrow A_4$
23/10/2023	2	A_6	$A_4 \rightarrow A_6$
	--	----	-----
21/03/2024	22	A_7	$A_6 \rightarrow A_7, A_4, A_7, A_7, A_6, A_7$
28/03/2024	23	A_7	$A_7 \rightarrow A_4, A_6, A_5, A_6, A_6, A_7$

Step 5: Generate all m – order time – variant FRGs

In this study, we apply the concept of time - variant fuzzy relationship group [25] to create FRGs. Based on the current state of the FRs in Table 4, the FRs can be grouped into a FRG by considering the history of appearance of the fuzzy sets on the next state of the FRs, and called Time variant-FRGs. From this viewpoint, we obtain all 1st-order time –variant FRGs, which are shown in Table 5. Where, there are 30 groups in training phase and one group in testing phase.

Table 5: The Complete The 1st–Order Time Variant Frgs

No	1st– order FRs	1st – order TV- FRGs
G1	$A_5 \rightarrow A_5$	$A_5 \rightarrow A_5$
G2	$A_5 \rightarrow A_6$	$A_5 \rightarrow A_6$
----	-----	-----
G22	$A_6 \rightarrow A_7$	$A_6 \rightarrow A_7, A_4, A_7, A_7, A_6, A_7$
G23	$A_7 \rightarrow A_7$	$A_7 \rightarrow A_4, A_6, A_5, A_6, A_6, A_7$
G24	$A_7 \rightarrow \#$	$A_7 \rightarrow \#$

Step 6: Defuzzify and compute the forecasting output values

The last step is to defuzzify the forecasting values to a crisp output value by fuzzy forecasting rules. In particular, in order to defuzzify the fuzzified data values, the our defuzzified principle in article [25] is presented to compute the forecasted value for all 1st – order and high – order time variant FRGs in training phase. Next, we use a defuzzified principle [26] for computing with the unknown linguistic value in testing phase. The forecasting principles is presented as follows:

Rule 1: Calculate the forecasting value with known linguistic values

To obtain the forecasting output results of proposed model from the time variant - FRGs. we divide each corresponding interval with respect to the linguistic value in the next state into four sub-intervals which has the same length, and calculate forecasted output value for each group according to in (6).

$$FV = \frac{1}{2*n} \sum_{i=1}^n (subm_{ik} + Value_lu_{ik}) \quad (6)$$

Where, FV is forecasted value at time t , n is the sum of fuzzy sets on the next state of FRG.

- $subm_{ik}$ denotes the midpoint value of one of four sub-intervals ($1 \leq k \leq 4$) with respect to i -th linguistic value in the next state of FRG that the real data at forecasting time falls into this sub-interval.
- $Value_lu_{ik}$ is one of two values belonging to the lower bound and upper bound value of one of three sub-intervals which has the real data at forecasting time falls within sub-interval u_{ik} (e.g, $u_{ik} = [L_{ik}, U_{ik}]$).
- If the historical data value at forecasting time smaller than midpoint value of sub-interval u_{ik} , then $Value_lu_{ik}$ is assigned as the lower bound of sub-interval u_{ik}

- If the historical data value at forecasting time larger than midpoint value of sub-interval u_{ik} , $Value_lu_{ik}$ is assigned as the upper bound of sub-interval u_{ik}

Rule 2: Calculate the forecasting value with unknown linguistic values

In the testing phase, we calculate forecasting value for the group of fuzzy relationship which has the unknown linguistic value appearing in the next state. Assume that there is the m -th order fuzzy relationship group whose next state is $\#$, shown as follows: $A_{i\ m}, A_{i\ m-1}, \dots, A_{i\ 1} \rightarrow \#$.

Where the symbol “ $\#$ ” denotes an unknown value, then the forecasted value of year i is identified according to [26] as follows:

$$FV = m_{i1} + \frac{\sum_{k=2}^m m_{i(k-1)} - m_{ik}}{2^{k-1}} \quad (7)$$

where, $m_{i1}, m_{i2}, \dots, m_{ik}$ is midpoints of u_{i1}, u_{i2}, \dots , and u_{ik} ($2 \leq k \leq m$), respectively.

Based on two forecasting principles above, we complete forecasting results for Gas prices RON95 in Vietnam from 02/10/2023 to 28/03/2024 based on 1st-order time variant-FRGs under seven intervals, which are listed in Table 6.

Table 6: The Complete Forecasted Results Based On The 1st- Order Time Variant Frgs

Day	RON 95 data	Fuzzy sets	Forecasted values
02/10/2023	24840	A_7	Not forecasted
11/10/2023	23040	A_4	22936.2
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21/03/2024	24280	A_7	23894.4
28/03/2024	24810	A_7	23564.3

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The present study demonstrates the application of the proposed method with two experiments. Experiment 1 compares the accuracy of its forecasted results with some conventional models and experiment 2 illustrates the improvements in the proposed model.

4.1. Datasets and evaluation criterion

Since fuzzy time series forecasting models have been used to make predictions in enrolments for many years, we also investigate enrollments at the University of Alabama [3] from 1971 to 1992 and the datasets of Gas prices RON95 in Vietnam which was collected from <https://vnexpress.net/kinhdoanh/hang-hoa>. To confirm the effectiveness of proposed forecasting model on two theses datasets, mean square error (MSE) and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) are employed as an evaluation criterion in term of the forecasted accuracy. The MSE and MAPE can be calculated as follows:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=m}^n (Fo_i - Re_i)^2 \quad (8)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=m}^n \left| \frac{Fo_i - Re_i}{Re_i} \right| * 100\% \quad (9)$$

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Where Re_i, Fo_i represent the real value and forecasting value at year i , respectively; n is the total number of forecasted data, m means the order of the FR.

4.2. Applying to forecast the enrollments of the University of Alabama

In this section, we evaluate proposed forecasting model in education domain on enrolments data of University of Alabama and compared the obtained results with previous prediction models [3, 31-35] to demonstrate the performance of our method. The obtained forecasting results from the proposed

model which are shown in Table 7. To visualize, Figure 4 illustrates the first-order fuzzy time series forecasting model and contrasts it with actual enrollments and other existing models. The results in Table 7 show that the proposed model has the MSE(8) value of 43906.6 which is the smallest among all the models compared with number of intervals equal to 7. From forecasted values in Table 7 and Figure 4, it can be seen that the proposed model gives a very positive predictive effect on the enrollments problem of the University of Alabama.

Fig. 4: The charts depict real data in comparison with other models and the proposed model.

Table 7. A Comparison Of The Existing Models In Enrollments Dataset With The Proposed Model

Years	Actual enrolments	Model [3]	Model [32]	Model [33]	Model [31]	Model [34]	Model [35]	Proposed model
1971	13055							
1972	13563	14000	14025	15430	14230	14195	14242.0	13610.6
1973	13867	14000	14568	15430	14230	14424	14242.0	13841.3
1974	14696	14000	14568	15430	14230	14593	14242.0	14740
1975	15460	15500	15654	15430	15541	15589	15474.3	15454.3
1976	15311	16000	15654	15430	15541	15645	15474.3	15308.8
1977	15603	16000	15654	15430	15541	15634	15474.3	15606.4
1978	15861	16000	15654	15430	16196	16100	15474.3	15574
1979	16807	16000	16197	16889	16196	16188	16146.5	16768.1
1980	16919	16833	17283	16871	16196	17077	16988.3	16951.7
1981	16388	16833	17283	16871	17507	17105	16988.3	16673
1982	15433	16833	16197	15447	16196	16369	16146.5	15430
1983	15497	16000	15654	15430	15541	15643	15474.3	15560.7
1984	15145	16000	15654	15430	15541	15648	15474.3	15824.2
1985	15163	16000	15654	15430	15541	15622	15474.3	15126.7
1986	15984	16000	15654	15430	15541	15623	15474.3	15761.6
1987	16859	16000	16197	16889	16196	16231	16146.5	16768.1
1988	18150	16833	17283	16871	17507	17090	16988.3	18142.9
1989	18970	19000	18369	19333	18872	18325	19144.0	18897.1
1990	19328	19000	19454	19333	18872	19000	19144.0	19103
1991	19337	19000	19454	19333	18872	19000	19144.0	19705.2

1992	18876	19000	19454	19333	18872	19000	19144.0	18689
MSE		407507	255227.4	446761.76	261162.3	261463.62	228920	43906.6

In addition, the forecasted results of the proposed model are also compared with each model which is named as in works [6, 18, 4, 20] based on the various high - order FRs with different number of intervals. Comparison of these models according to the MSE (8) value is shown in Fig 5, where the CC06b model in work [20] model and the C02 model in work [4] use 7th-order and 5th- order FRs, respectively. Remaining models use fuzzy relations with number of orders less equal to 4. The results in Fig. 5 confirm that our proposed model has the smallest error in comparison with four other models in terms of MSE.

Fig. 5. A comparison of the MSE value between the proposed model and various high-order FTS models.

For the proposed model, the MSE value is 537.4 which is the smallest forecasting error as known. It can be seen that the proposed model forecasts more accurate than the existing models for various high-order models under different number of intervals.

4.3. Applying to forecast the Gasonline price of RON 95

In this section, the proposed model is applied to forecast the Gas prices RON95 in Vietnam between 02/10/2023 and 28/03/2024. The performance of the proposed model is evaluated by using the MAPE (9). The results and accuracy of the proposed model based on different number of orders with 7 intervals which are shown in Table 8. Furthermore, the trend in forecast of the proposed method is also illustrated in Fig. 5 and it clearly shows that the proposed forecasted values are significantly in close accordance with the actual values.

Table 8. The Forecasting Results And Accuracy Of The Proposed Model

Day	Actual data of RON95	Forecasted values
02/10/2023	24840	Not forecasted
11/10/2023	23040	22936.2
23/10/2023	23510	23542.9
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21/03/2024	24280	24394.4
28/03/2024	24810	23964.3
MAPE		1.22%

Fig.5. A describe graph between actual versus forecasted values of the proposed model.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we introduce a FTS forecasting model utilizing a graph-based clustering technique, with the objective of achieving enhanced forecasting accuracy. The proposed method addresses a limitation of existing fuzzy time series forecasting approaches by automating the determination of interval lengths in the universal of discourse. Specifically, our approach employs the graph-based clustering technique to dynamically determine interval lengths, eliminating the need for pre-selecting the number of intervals by the user. Furthermore, we define time variant fuzzy relationship groups and compute forecasted values using simple computation rather than relying on the max-min composition operator on fuzzy sets. The effectiveness of proposed method is evaluated by using datasets concerning student enrollments at the University of Alabama and Gas prices RON95 in Vietnam. Our simulation and application results suggest that our approach contributes meaningfully to the literature on time series clustering.

In future research, we propose extending our model to accommodate two-factor FTS forecasting and exploring new approaches such as employing particle swarm optimization and neural networks to further enhance forecasting accuracy.

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